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Benthic process model developments

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List of abbreviations

WW	Wet weight
DW	Dry weight
AFDW	Ash-free dry weight
C	Carbon
N	Nitrogen
P	Phosphorus
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
DEB-IBM	Dynamic Energy Budget – Individual Based Model
ERSEM	European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model
BAMHBI	Biogeochemical Model for Hypoxic and Benthic Influenced areas
NEMO	Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean
MWTL	Monitoring Waterstaatkundige Toestand des Lands, Dutch aquatic environment monitoring programme
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
SIM	Suspended Inorganic Matter
FABM	Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents advances in process-based models for benthic ecosystems developed under NECCTON Work Package 6, focusing on sea-bottom flora and fauna (Task 6.2.4). Benthic ecosystems – the communities living on and in the seafloor – play crucial roles in marine food webs, support fisheries, and regulate biogeochemical cycles. However, predicting their dynamics remains challenging due to limited availability of observational data and incomplete understanding of key processes. The work addresses critical gaps in benthic ecosystem modelling by delivering three new products: benthic macrofaunal biomass by functional type (deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and newly introduced predators), filter-feeding bivalve (*Mytilus*) growth and biomass, and red seaweed (*Phyllophora*) biomass.

The **European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM)** was enhanced by inclusion of two new macrofaunal predator groups, **infaunal and epifaunal predators**, to improve representation of the benthic food web and the biomasses of already existing groups – deposit and suspension feeders. Key findings include:

- To improve model validation, analysis of long-term data from Station L4 revealed high spatial variability in benthic macrofauna biomass, detecting only limited seasonal patterns.
- Literature review of ingestion rates showed current ERSEM parameter values fall within observed ranges, though high variability limits further constraints.
- Inclusion of benthic predators combined with shear stress corrections significantly improved model predictions across Dutch North Sea locations.
- 3D testing: Regional implementation on the North West European Shelf demonstrated realistic spatial patterns of benthic macrofauna, while implicitly accounting for organic matter trapping within permeable sediments.

Two complementary models were developed for the Black Sea's unique biogeochemical environment:

- ***Mytilus* DEB-IBM model:** A Dynamic Energy Budget Individual-Based Model for *Mytilus galloprovincialis* was developed and calibrated using growth data from three Black Sea locations. The model successfully predicts individual growth and population dynamics, showing good agreement with biomass observations. Spatial predictions reveal highest

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biomasses on the shallow northwestern shelf, with no viable populations in the deep anoxic central zone.

- **Phyllophora seaweed model:** A physiological model for red seaweed *Phyllophora* incorporates colour-specific photosynthesis and light attenuation crucial for deep-water macroalgae. The model accounts for competition with *Cystoseira* communities and predicts biomass responses to varying turbidity and depth conditions, providing insights into habitat suitability under eutrophication scenarios.

This document should be read alongside NECCTON D6.1, which defines new benthic products, and NECCTON D5.2, which details pelagic model process developments.

Model code for ERSEM benthic macrofauna is available via NECCTON GitHub repository at <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ersem- neccton/tree/benthic-fauna> , and for the *Mytilus* and *Phyllophora* models at https://github.com/QMudde/Benthic_Process_models.

2. Introduction

2.1 Scope of the document

This document describes the process-based model developments undertaken within NECCTON WP6, which focuses on benthic processes linked to sea bottom flora and fauna. The document covers the current state and capabilities of the models, assumptions underlying new developments, and results from testing new parameterisations and formulations.

The work performed within Task 6.2.4 supports delivery of three new products: 1) benthic macrofaunal biomass by functional type (deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and newly added benthic predators), 2) filter-feeding bivalve growth and biomass (*Mytilus*), and 3) red seaweed biomass (*Phyllophora*).

Development of benthic process models remains challenging due to insufficient understanding of process dynamics and scarcity of observational data. Although Copernicus Marine Service products do not currently include benthic variables, the developments within NECCTON WP6 provide a strong foundation for their inclusion.

This document should be read alongside NECCTON D6.1, which defines new benthic products, and NECCTON D5.2, which details pelagic model process developments.

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2.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows. Section 3 provides a general overview of the model systems, focusing on description of the processes parameterised within NECCTON task 6.2.4. These modelling systems are benthic modules of European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM), the DEB-IBM model for mussel growth and population biomass, and a physiological process model of seaweed *Phyllophora*. Section 4 provides a detailed description of model improvements and developments divided into two main subsections according to the geographical regions where these developments were implemented and tested. For ERSEM, implemented on the North West European Shelf (4.2), subsections describe a) exploration of long-term observational data for improving model validation, b) analysis of key model parameters, c) impact of incorporation of benthic predators on macrofaunal biomass across functional types, and d) testing new developments in 3D. For the Black Sea (4.2), subsections describe the following model developments: a) calibration and performance of the *Mytilus* DEB model; b) predictions of *Mytilus* biomass and density with the DEB-IBM model, and c) the physiological model of red seaweed *Phyllophora* growth and biomass. The report concludes with a summary. The beginning of the report provides a reference list of key abbreviations.

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3. General overview of the model systems

3.1 European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM)

We applied the ecosystem-biogeochemical model ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016), originally developed to simulate the ecosystem dynamics of the lower trophic level of the North Sea (Baretta et al., 1995), now extensively applied on the Northwest European Shelf (NWES) to address research questions, support decision making and sustainable management of marine resources. Among other models, it is also used as the biogeochemical model component in Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS) reanalysis. NWES region is a highly dynamic and complex environment characterised by strong gradients in depth, mixing regimes, and land-ocean interactions, supporting diverse benthic ecosystems and close coupling between pelagic and benthic environments.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of pools and processes in the biogeochemical model ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016).

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The model incorporates key processes in both pelagic and benthic environments and explicitly includes a representation of benthic-pelagic coupling through the exchange of particulate and dissolved material (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Modelled organisms in ERSEM are grouped into several functional types according to their primary form of feeding/energy acquisition, enabling parsimony and ensuring model efficiency at a range of scales, from regional to global. In its standard configuration, the ERSEM pelagic components include four groups of primary producers, three groups of zooplankton and a single explicit pool of bacteria. The benthic components include two groups of benthic macrofauna (suspension feeders and deposit feeders), meiofauna, and aerobic and anaerobic bacterial groups (Table 1). All these groups mediate the cycling of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and silicon in the modelled environment. Notably, modelled groups of benthic macrofauna contribute, to a varying extent, to bioturbation and bioirrigation. NECCTON expands the benthic configuration of ERSEM by introducing two additional macrofaunal groups: infaunal and epifaunal predators (Figure 2). Given our primary aim of improving model representation of suspension and deposit feeders, we explored two alternative routes: a) adjusting model parameter values, and b) changing the model food web structure. The latter was identified as a viable route towards improvement of model performance, as detailed in later chapters of this report.

Table 1: Benthic macrofaunal functional types and their food sources in the standard ERSEM configuration (Butenschön et al., 2016) and those added in NECCTON.

Functional type	Food sources	ERSEM configuration
Deposit feeders	Benthic particulate organic matter (POM), meiofauna and bacteria.	Standard
Suspension feeders	Near-bottom POM and phytoplankton, sediment surface POM.	Standard
Infaunal predators	Macrofauna within bottom sediments	NECCTON
Epibenthic predators	Macrofauna close to the sediment surface	NECCTON

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Figure 2. Conceptual diagram of stocks and fluxes within ERSEM benthic modules extended with representation of epibenthic and infaunal predators.

Within NECCTON we have implemented ERSEM in two distinct modes. First, we investigated the effects of introducing predator groups on the model performance in a 0D (box-model) offline mode, examining benthic system dynamics at select locations, forced with outputs (near-bottom temperature, shear stress, phytoplankton and particulate organic matter concentrations) from preexisting NEMO-ERSEM simulations (see section 4.1.3). Results of these simulations have informed experiments in fully coupled mode, applying the NEMO-ERSEM system to the entire Northwest European Shelf (section 4.1.4). ERSEM implementation in FABM facilitates the applied flexibility of online/offline coupling across scales (Bruggeman & Bolding, 2014).

3.2 DEB-IBM for mussel growth and population biomass in the Black Sea

The BAMHBI model describes the unique biogeochemistry of the Black Sea (Grégoire et al., 2025). This model was developed to incorporate the unusual hypoxia and eutrophication that have affected the Black Sea ecosystem for decades. The BAMHBI model does not yet incorporate macrobenthic organisms, although this inclusion could be important for the biogeochemistry itself as well as benthic ecosystem conservation, fisheries, and aquaculture.

Filter feeders define a crucial part of benthic ecosystem functioning because they directly link pelagic carbon and benthic biomass by feeding on suspended particles. The filter feeding bivalve, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, is the dominant shellfish in the Black Sea both in natural areas and as a target for aquaculture. Here, within the NECCTON framework, we have developed and calibrated a Dynamic Energy Budget (DEB) model for Black Sea *M. galloprovincialis* to predict growth and reproduction (Figure 3).

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Figure 3: Schematic representation of the *Mytilus galloprovincialis* DEB model.

The individual DEB model for *M. galloprovincialis* is driven by 3 classic individual specific variables often used in DEB theory: Reserves, Structure, and Reproduction buffer (Kooijman, 2009). Based in the physiology of an individual animal, this model can predict physical and ecological outputs, such as length-at-age and released gametes. Classic DEB theory implements assimilation based on a dimensionless feeding response using a generalized food concentration in the environment and species-specific parameters, usually only allowing two dynamic environmental factors, temperature and a generic food concentration. Here, we implemented a suspension feeder-specific feeding mechanism, originally derived by Saraiva et al. (2011) to differentiate between high quality (phytoplankton) and low quality (detritus) food as well as inhibiting suspended silt particles. Additionally, we implemented oxygen dependence in the individual physiology based on experiments by Jansen et al. (2009), because hypoxia is such a determining ecological factor in the Black Sea. By doing so, we can calibrate and implement this model over a broader, biogeochemically heterogeneous spatial range as a result of the flexibility of the model to react to different suspended matter concentrations and types. The model can be run in constant (Figure 4) or dynamic (Figure 5) environmental conditions, with possible dynamic environmental forcings including: temperature, phytoplankton, detritus, suspended inorganic matter (SIM), and oxygen. The individual model is run in 0D, does not incorporate factors such as settlement or probability of occurrence, and does not depend on any additional local variables such as depth or shear stress.

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Additional ecological processes such as mortality or reproduction are only implemented in the individual DEB model through biomass release during spawning periods (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Main output of *M. galloprovincialis* DEB model runs, individual physiology. Four different constant conditions are used as forcings: high temperature & high food (black), high temperature & low food (red), low temperature & high food (green), low temperature & low food (blue). “STRUCT” refers to structural carbon, “RESERVE” refers to reserve carbon “REPROD” refers to total carbon in reproduction tissues, the sum of gonads and gametes and “Length” refers to the actual predicted shell length as measured in the field.

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Figure 5: Main output of the *M. galloprovincialis* DEB model runs, individual physiology. Four different dynamic conditions are used as forcings, high oxygen & high silt (black), high oxygen & low silt (red), low oxygen & high silt (green), low oxygen & low silt (blue). “STRUCT” refers to structural carbon, “RESERVE” refers to reserve carbon “REPROD” refers to total carbon in reproduction tissues, the sum of gonads and gametes and “Length” refers to the actual predicted shell length as measured in the field.

As an extension of the individual DEB physiology model, we also developed a dynamic *M. galloprovincialis* population model (Figure 6). This model tracks population biomass and abundance of several cohorts of mussels, simulating a mussel bed. Each separate cohort tracks an individual DEB physiological model, and we assume that individuals of each cohort broadly follow this ‘average DEB individual’ in terms of Reserve, Structure, and Reproduction buffer. In turn, at predefined biannual spawning periods, all individuals in the mussel bed release their gametes as pelagic eggs that hatch into larvae in the water column. These larvae grow in terms of individual biomass, rapidly reduce in numbers through high per capita mortality in their larval stage, and ultimately settle into a new cohort of sessile mussels once an individual reaches a biomass threshold. Settlement of pelagic larvae depends on shear stress and sediment type.

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Figure 6: Schematic representation of the *Mytilus galloprovincialis* DEB-IBM

Total mussel bed biomass and density decrease through population-based mortality effects, and increase through combined individual feeding, growth, and reproduction processes of all individual mussels. Mortality terms consist of per capita larval mortality, per capita mussel mortality, heat mortality, increased mortality for juvenile cohorts and increased mortality for cohorts with a relatively low individual reserve/structure ratio (partial starvation). Cohort specific mortality rates relate closely to the DEB state of the average individual in that cohort. Erratic population behaviour characterizes the final DEB-IBM with high seasonality; therefore, we chose to represent estimates of mussel bed biomass and density via 1-year and 2-year averages (Figure 7). Model formulation and parametrization of both *Mytilus* models can be found at: https://github.com/QMudde/Benthic_Process_models.

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Figure 7: Population density and biomass trajectories as predicted by the DEB-IBM for *M. galloprovincialis*. The average year of near bottom environmental forcings from a Black Sea location ($x = 28.77$, $y = 44.12$) are chosen to show this example, data are from CMEMS and NEMO-BAMHBI. The black line represents the direct model output, the dashed red line is a 1-year average, and the solid red line shows the 2-year average.

3.3 *Phyllophora* seaweed process model of the Black Sea, seaweed physiology.

Besides macrobenthic fauna, macrobenthic flora also potentially determine the biogeochemistry of the Black Sea. The dominant benthic flora species in the Black Sea are *Phyllophora* redweeds, *Cystoseira* brownweeds, and *Zostera* seagrasses. Here, we developed a model to track individual physiological processes of *Phyllophora* (Figure 8). *Phyllophora* fields are a crucial component of the benthic habitat in the Black Sea, given that they produce oxygen, extract nutrients from the environment, and provide habitat and structure to a range of macrobenthic lifeforms (Stevens et al., 2019). However, *Phyllophora* biomass has critically declined in the last 100 years since the discovery of the Zernov's *Phyllophora* Field (ZPF) (Milchakova et al., 2013), and has only recently received protection (Kostylev et al., 2010).

Here, within the NECCTON framework, we have built upon previous macroalgae model research (Broch & Slagstad, 2012; Hadley et al., 2015; Vasechkina et al., 2020) and present a physiological macroalgae model, that can be used to analyse and understand *Phyllophora* biomass dynamics of the Black Sea. With the developed model, we aim to provide a tool to allow researchers to gain a better understanding of the reduction in seaweed biomass in the Black Sea as well as improved capabilities to predict potential recovery in the future and the possible impact of *Phyllophora*-covered sediment on biogeochemical cycles in terms of oxygen and macronutrients.

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The macroalgae process model predicts algal biomass based on four main state variables: C-Reserves, N-Reserves, P-Reserves and Structural biomass (Figure 8). Structural biomass has a maximal biomass specific growth rate that is limited by the most limiting nutrient dependent on the three reserve pools. It also has a constant biomass specific mortality and density dependent erosion. Nutrient reserve pools are filled by direct nutrient uptake from the environment via a Monod-equation and internal Droop kinetics for nutrient saturation (Figure 8). Carbon reserves are filled through photosynthesis and lost through maintenance and growth respiration. If the C-reserve pool is relatively full, exudation extrudes part of the assimilation product, but if the C-reserve pool is too low to account for maintenance respiration, structural biomass is lost to compensate, a process known as structural regression. The combination of the physiological state of the *Phyllophora* biomass, temperature mortality, and erosion, result in a net biomass specific growth rate (Figure 9). A positive long-term net-growth rate is only available in suitable habitats for *Phyllophora*, in terms of dissolved macronutrients and light. The model specifically distinguishes between three different bands of light within the Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) range, because of the deep distribution of *Phyllophora* and the optical properties of different light colours that travel through deep waters. As red seaweeds, *Phyllophora* have a specific preference for non-red colours of light for their photosynthetic activity, which are also the colours within PAR that penetrate deepest into the water column. To correctly model depth dispersal of the seaweed, especially under eutrophic circumstances in the Black Sea, we implemented colour-specific photosynthesis and light attenuation based on blue (400-500 nm), green (500-600 nm), and red (600-700 nm) light. The parametrization incorporates data on colour-specific light attenuation by seawater and chlorophyll (Gallegos et al., 1990; Nababan et al., 2021) as well as data on colour affinity of *Phyllophora* thalli (Lüning & Dring, 1985).

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Figure 8: Schematic representation of the macroalgal biomass model, calibrated for Black Sea *Phyllophora*.

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Figure 9: Example physiology of the macroalgae model, based on a 3-year run. Upper 6 panels show environmental forcings of the example run, and the lower 6 panels show *Phyllophora* physiological rates, expressed per m². The black line denotes the model forced by constant conditions, the red line denotes the model forced by ‘simple’ dynamic conditions, and the blue line denotes the model forced by ‘realistic’ dynamic conditions. The data for realistic forcings were extracted from CMEMS at 45°N, 30°E, and represent the average year values at the seafloor (and sea surface for irradiance).

Biomass, the main output variable of the macroalgae model, is expressed as net-growth rate, in wet weight per m². Figure 10 shows the modelled response of *Phyllophora* biomass at a Black Sea location (45°N, 30°E) with repeated average years as environmental forcings (Figure 10). The model is run for 12 years to show the stabilizing of *Phyllophora* biomass under certain depth and turbidity conditions. Different turbidity and depth levels show the response of *Phyllophora* habitat suitability to eutrophication. A growth rate analysis of *Phyllophora* under a range of depth and turbidity conditions showed the decrease of possible living growth habitat under increasing eutrophication conditions (Figure 11). This model assessment assumes that *Phyllophora* competes for light with *Cystoseira* biomass at shallower depths, *Cystoseira* community biomass (WW) is roughly distributed with depth expressed as the function $WW = a - (b * depth) * c$, where $a = 1500$, $b = 18$ and $c = 1.5$. Values are based on Black Sea *Cystoseira* community assessments conducted by Afanasyev et al. (2017). Model formulation and parametrization can be found at:

https://github.com/QMudde/Benthic_Process_models.

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Figure 10: Macroalgae model, calibrated for Black Sea *Phyllophora*, run at a sample location (45°N, 30°E), forced by repeated time series of average year of environmental forcings. Environmental data are from Copernicus Marine Service. 4 model runs show effect of turbidity, solid line is turbid ($k_0 = 0.12$ [1/m]), dashed line is clear water ($k_0 = 0.03$ [1/m]), and effect of depth (black lines are 15 m deep, red lines are 30 m deep). Model is run for 12 years to show biomass stability over longer time scales.

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Figure 11: Heatmap of net growth rate values resulting from the *Phyllophora* model under a range of depth and turbidity conditions. Green cells denote habitat conditions where *Phyllophora* has a positive net-growth rate, blue cells have a net-negative growth rate. The plots show 3 general areas within the tested parameter space: A) habitat conditions where *Phyllophora* biomass can grow to a stable population, B) habitat where depth and turbidity limit light penetration towards the bottom as the main limiting factor for *Phyllophora* growth, C) habitat where *Phyllophora* has negative growth rate resulting from competition with *Cystoseira*-dominated macroalgae communities. The left plot shows outcome without accounting for Chlorophyll-a in the overlaying water column; the right plot includes Chlorophyll-a as an additional layer of shading.

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4. Model developments

4.1 North West European Shelf

4.1.1 Towards improving model validation with long-term seasonality-resolving observational data

Availability of high-quality observational data with appropriate spatial and temporal resolution is instrumental for the evaluation of model performance and guiding new model developments and improvements. Data availability has always been a challenge for modelling the benthic environment, where data is scarce compared to the pelagic counterpart, and limited in spatial as well as temporal coverage. Matching observed and modelled quantities that may have not only different measurement units but also represent different or misaligned concepts and quantities adds a major challenge.

Availability of observational data on benthic macrofauna is relatively greater among variables represented in ERSEM benthic modules. For the purpose of this work, we have identified three main data sources on the NWES. The ICES North Sea Benthos Survey (Aldridge et al., 2007; Künitzer et al., 1992) provides a snapshot of spatial distribution of benthic macrofauna in the Southern and Central North Sea in 1986, including abundance and biomass at a higher taxonomic level (phyla and class). Dutch field monitoring data, the Monitoring Waterstaatkundige Toestand des Lands (MWTL), includes observations of species, densities, and biomasses of the benthic macrofauna within the Dutch region of the North Sea, providing long-term time series since 1995 at yearly intervals. The Western Channel Observatory collects abundance and biomass of benthic fauna at Station L4 (50.2° N, -4.2° E). Five replicate box cores collected at approximately monthly intervals provide a unique data set for assessing seasonality and variability in the distribution of benthic fauna.

In ERSEM, benthic variables tend to show pronounced seasonality in shallow productive regions, as shown in Lessin et al (2019), who used the model to interpret temporal changes of major macrozoobenthic feeding groups at Station L4 during 2008–2013. However, because benthic survey continued beyond that period, longer time series are now available, and some within-year gaps have been filled (McEvoy et al., 2023). In analysing these updated time series, our main objectives were: a) to evaluate seasonal variability and interannual trends in benthic macrofauna at Station L4 based on the updated dataset, and b) to assess whether seasonally resolved data at Station L4 can be used to complement the yearly MWTL data, informing intra-year dynamics of macrofaunal groups and enhancing reliability of model validation in this region.

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Around 800 species or taxa have been identified at Station L4. ERSEM models benthic fauna as functional types based on feeding mode (rather than size, used as a primary category in the pelagic). Comparing model output to observations requires sorting species into their respective functional types. Various datasets and methods are available for this exercise. Here, we applied two approaches. First, we assigned each species a feeding type within the standard ERSEM configuration (i.e. suspension or deposit feeders) applying (Beauchard et al., 2023) trait dataset and expanding to species identified only at L4 using taxonomic information from the World Register of Marine Species (<https://www.marinespecies.org>) using R package *worms* (Chamberlain & Vanhoorne, 2024). In our second approach, we sorted species into suspension feeders, deposit feeders, herbivores, and predators based on (Beauchard et al., 2022) trait dataset, and using the R package *Btrait* (<https://github.com/EMODnet/Btrait>; (Soetaert & Beauchard, 2023)). Our analysis did not consider herbivores because they make up very little of the biomass at L4 across the time series (mean: 0.78 %, median: 0.25 %), and ERSEM thus does not represent them as a standalone group. We have also analysed separately *unidentifiable biomass*, which is comprised of parts of organisms that cannot be identified but are weighed to give the most accurate measure of total zoobenthic biomass in box core samples. Consecutively, *total biomass* represents all zoobenthic biomass within a replicate.

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Figure 122: Feeding types (deposit feeders and suspension feeders) estimated using *Beauchard et al (2023)* dataset, unidentifiable biomass and total biomass at Station L4. Unidentifiable and total biomass are independent of the conversion factors used. Points show replicate-level observations, lines show the trend across the time series, fitted with two parameters (intercept and slope) in log-space as the data is lognormally distributed. A solid line indicates the slope is significant at $p \leq 0.15$, a dashed line indicates that $p > 0.15$.

Figure 133: Feeding types estimated using Btrait: deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and predators. Points show replicate-level observations, lines show the trend across the time series, fitted with two parameters (intercept and slope) in log-space as the data is lognormally distributed. A solid line indicates the slope is significant at $p \leq 0.15$, a dashed line indicates that $p > 0.15$.

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Both sets of conversions resulted in higher average biomass for suspension feeders than deposit feeders (Figures 12, 13). Suspension feeder and deposit feeder biomasses were lower when we used Btrait to assign feeding types, because of allocation of some of the biomass to predators (Figure 13). We explored the groups of biomass for trends across the time series by applying a linear fit in log space, given that the data were lognormally distributed. The only significant trend at $p < 0.05$ was unidentifiable biomass, which increased 1.15 g per year. Total biomass increased by 1.97 g per year and predators decreased by 0.17 g per year. Both were not significant at a $p = 0.1$ significance level. Other groups yielded either no trend or a non-significant trend at a significance level of $p = 0.15$.

Table 2: Abbreviations and full names of different measures of biomass.

Full name	Abbreviation
Wet weight	WW
Dry weight	DW
Ash-free dry weight	AFDW
Carbon	C

To compare observations of benthic macrofaunal biomass directly to modelled data required converting biomass measured in wet weight to carbon units. The conversion to carbon units used the Brey et al. (2010) dataset, which provides different conversion factors from wet weight to carbon, mapping values according to taxonomic proximity using the `worms` R-package (Chamberlain & Vanhoorne, 2024). Benthic faunal observations include the shells and skeletons of organisms, but this part of the biomass is not modelled in ERSEM and therefore should ideally be excluded during conversions. One method converts wet weight to ash-free dry weight. The non-organic part of the weight which comprises shells and skeletons does not burn off at high temperatures and therefore remains as ash. This value is then subtracted to calculate the ash-free dry weight. Where this data is not available, the proportion of the biomass comprised of shell can be removed using the ratio of wet weight to wet weight including shell. If neither of these conversions are available, we used dry weight conversions without removing the proportion of shell or skeleton biomass. Some taxa (e.g. polychaetes) lack shells or skeletons and therefore do not require subtraction of this proportion of biomass during conversions.

Depending on the availability of conversion factors, we followed three possible pathways to calculate the ratio of carbon to wet weight, in order of preference (Table 2):

- 1) $C:AFDW \times AFDW:WW$
- 2) $C:DW \times DW:WW \times WW:[WW + shell]$
- 3) $C:DW \times DW:WW$

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In some cases, when no conversion factor was available for a taxonomically related species, species could not be matched to generate a conversion. For these species, we used the mean value for the conversion from wet weight to carbon at a functional group level. These C:WW ratios were determined to be 0.065 for suspension feeders, and 0.077 for deposit feeders and predators.

There are very limited data (~40 measurements) available in Brey et al (2010) for carbon:ash free dry weight ratios, forcing us to match species and conversion factor at a class and order level, depending on data availability. This constraint leads to very high uncertainty in estimates and could mean that using a constant conversion factor for all species may yield results of similar accuracy.

Brey et al. 2010 includes C:AFDW data from:

- 19 species within the class Malacostraca (mean – 0.52)
- 16 species within the order Decapoda (mean – 0.51)
- 6 species within the class Copepoda (mean – 0.46)

To investigate how using constant conversion factors of C:AFDW affects the resulting carbon biomasses associated with the paucity of conversion factors for individual groups, we carried out a sensitivity analysis using constant values for all species. Here, we used monthly average biomass values across the 12 years of WCO benthic survey. The variability in carbon biomass was consistently dominated by replicate level variability rather than the uncertainty in the conversion factor, which had a much smaller effect (Figure 144).

Figure 144: Impact of uncertainty in the conversion from ash-free dry mass to carbon on the resulting carbon biomasses for deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and total biomass. Solid line shows the mean, shaded area indicates boundaries of one standard deviation.

To investigate whether the biomasses of benthic macrofauna at Station L4 followed distinct seasonal patterns, we fitted general additive models (GAMs) to the carbon mass data at a functional group level. Data were first transformed into log space to account for its lognormal

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distribution, thereafter models were fitted using gam function from R package mgcv (Wood, 2011). Cyclical cubic splines were used for the day of year to link the end of December to the beginning of January. Regular splines were used for the year.

These analyses revealed a bimodal, significant seasonal cycle for predators, with a peak in late spring and in autumn (Figure 17), in contrast to no seasonal cycle in deposit feeder and suspension feeder biomass (Figures 15 and 16). No significant interannual trend was observed in any of the functional groups. For all functional groups, seasonal or interannual variation explained only a small proportion of the variance, with the adjusted R-squared < 0.05.

The low explanation of variance by seasonal and interannual trends suggests that other factors influence biomass. High replicate level variability (Figure 14) likely reflects spatial variability rather than temporal variability given that all replicate samples are collected at the same time. Spatial heterogeneity could be caused by clustering of organisms in particular locations or by high variability in the size of zoobenthic organisms, which means that one large organism in a given box core could skew the entire sample biomass to be high. The lack of conversion factors adds a further challenge. The ERSEM model uses carbon as currency, but sample biomasses are measured in wet weight. Conversions are not available for all species. Although sensitivity to the conversion factor was relatively small compared to other sources of variability (Figure 14), more accurate conversions could help better constrain biomasses (Gogina et al., 2022).

Globally, there are few long-term time series stations where data is collected more than once a year. Low frequency sampling may lead to underestimation of variability, and changes that may be interpreted as significant may actually simply reflect the system's natural variability. Although model results exhibit strong seasonality, we were unable to extract a conclusive seasonal signal for benthic macrofaunal functional types from the 12-year time series of data available at Station L4.

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Figure 15: General additive model fit for seasonality (left) and interannual variability (right) for the deposit feeder carbon biomass at Station L4, where the y-axis label is the number of degrees of freedom used for the response variable smoothing function.

Figure 16: General additive model fit for seasonality (left) and interannual variability (right) for suspension feeder carbon biomass at Station L4, where the y-axis label is the number of degrees of freedom used for the response variable smoothing function.

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Figure 17: General additive model fit for seasonality (left) and interannual variability (right) for predator carbon biomass at Station L4, where the y-axis label is the number of degrees of freedom used for the response variable smoothing function.

4.1.2 Empirical justification for model parameter values

Marine biogeochemical models require estimation of values for many, often hundreds, of parameters that determine process rates. Many parameter values are challenging to constrain either resulting from a lack of published data on specific processes, or because the processes described in the model are not directly measurable in natural or laboratory settings. Some biogeochemical models, particularly those originally developed several decades ago, did not document the origins of parameter values, making them untraceable. We have no evidence whether they were based on published literature, previous modelling or experimental studies, model calibration exercises, or personal communication with empirical scientists. This ambiguity extends to many of the parameters in the benthic modules of ERSEM (Ebenhöh et al., 1995). We therefore reviewed the literature in an attempt to constrain key model parameters related to benthic macrofauna based on currently available data.

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Figure 185: Probability density function and probability histogram of deposit feeder specific maximum ingestion rate (d^{-1}) based on 60 measurements, standardised to $10^{\circ}C$. The area under the black curve has been normalised. The red line shows the value used in ERSEM, $0.11 d^{-1}$.

Figure 196: Probability density function and histogram of suspension feeder specific maximum ingestion rate (d^{-1}) from 38 measurements, standardised to $10^{\circ}C$. The area under the black curve has been normalised. The red line shows the value used in ERSEM, $0.09 d^{-1}$.

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Figure 207: Probability density function and histogram of predator specific maximum ingestion rate (d^{-1}) from 133 measurements, standardised to $10^{\circ}C$. The area under the black curve has been normalised. The red line shows the current value used in ERSEM for epibenthic predators, $0.03 d^{-1}$. The value used for infaunal predators in ERSEM is $0.08 d^{-1}$.

Ingestion rate is an important parameter for determining model outcomes, but its values are often calibrated to allow the model to align benthic fauna biomasses with observations, rather than constrained through measurements. We compared the values used in ERSEM to measurement data published in the literature, in particular the datasets compiled by Cammen, 1979) and Barrios-O'Neill et al(2019). Some modifications were needed to make the data more directly comparable to ERSEM.

- The maximum specific ingestion rates in ERSEM are specified at a temperature of $10^{\circ}C$, however observations were provided across a range of temperatures from 6 to $20^{\circ}C$. Therefore, observations were rescaled to $10^{\circ}C$ where necessary by dividing by the Q10 temperature scaling used in ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016).
- Species were collected into their respective feeding types, which had previously been assigned in Barrios-O'Neill et al (2019). To assign functional groups for the species from Cammen, 1979), we used the Beauchard et al (2023) trait dataset as described in 4.1.1 to split species between deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and predators.
- Where specific ingestion rate was unavailable, we divided the ingestion rate by the mass of the organism. Therefore, the specific rate was calculated from wet weight per wet weight for Barrios-O'Neill et al (2019) and dry weight per dry weight for Cammen (1979). Organism masses are expressed in mg C in ERSEM, and the conversion to carbon should ideally be

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considered because the higher trophic level is likely to be more energy dense than the lower trophic level. However, insufficient data is currently available to consider this approach.

We plotted histograms of the observations to compare to the values used in ERSEM for deposit feeders, suspension feeders, and predators (Figures 18-20). The model values were within the observed range, however, high variability in observed rates means we could not constrain the model values further. The different sizes of the organisms included in the data sets represented one of the key sources of variability. Size is a key determinant of physiological rates (Brown et al., 2004). To mitigate the influence of size on maximum ingestion rate, the model could consider explicitly including size in the future, bringing together the approach of size-spectrum models and the functional type approach of ERSEM. To facilitate this approach, several sources offer data on scaling of total biomass and ingestion rates with size (Durden et al., 2019; Kelly-Gerreyn et al., 2014; Labra et al., 2015; Schwinghamer et al., 1986).

4.1.3 Benthic macrofaunal predators: improving representation of benthic macrofaunal biomass across functional types

To analyse the accuracy of ERSEM macrobenthic biomass predictions we compared ERSEM model output with field measurements. The Dutch governmental organization Rijkswaterstaat performs a regular field monitoring campaign where they measure many aspects of the Dutch aquatic environment, the Monitoring Waterstaatkundige Toestand des Lands (MWTL). The MWTL data includes observations of species, densities and biomasses of the macrobenthos at several stations across the Dutch North Sea. For this analysis, we divided the North Sea MWTL stations into five general areas: Frisian front (FF), Dogger Bank (DB), Oyster Grounds (OG), Broad Fourteens north (BFN) and Broad Fourteens south (BFS), Figure 21. For each of those locations, we took the mean coordinates (shown on Figure 21 as the crosshairs), as the location to run the 0D ERSEM model and compare the model results with the mean macrobenthos biomass measurements of those stations (Figure 22).

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Figure 21: North Sea locations of MWTL stations and coordinates for associated model runs. See text for station abbreviations.

Figure 22: Example predictions of macrobenthos biomass from runs with the default benthic ERSEM, compared to field measurements. Lines are ERSEM model predictions, points are MWTL observations. Blue colours are suspension feeders; black colours are deposit feeders. Thin lines are daily values; thick lines are yearly mean values. Example locations are (left to right): Frisian Front (FF), Broad Fourteens north (BFN) and Dogger Bank (DB) (see Figure 21 map).

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Based on the results of the ERSEM run at the FF, BFN and DB central coordinate locations as an example (Figure 22), we conclude the current model does not accurately predict the biomass of macrobenthos. Although the model captures biomass of suspension feeders at FF, it overestimates biomass at BFN, and both model runs severely underestimate deposit feeder biomass, with predictions even dropping to 0 in instances where field measurements often show greater biomass of deposit feeders than suspension feeders in MWTL data. In the depositional area DB, in contrast, the model grossly overestimates deposit feeder biomass, noting that this was the only tested location where default ERSEM did not predict deposit feeder collapse.

The NECCTON project aims to improve benthic biomass predictions across functional types. Rather than adjusting highly uncertain model parameter values (see section 4.1.2), we focused on addressing key aspects of the model exerting bottom-up and top-down control on benthic macrofaunal communities, namely food supply to the benthos and predatory pressure. Bottom shear stress controls the former, whereas introduction of additional macrozoobenthic groups – infaunal and epifaunal predators – controls the latter.

First, we apply a correction to bottom shear stress. In ERSEM, the bottom stress affects dynamics of both deposition and resuspension/erosion of suspended material, and thus food supply to the benthic realm. In the case of dynamic locations such as FF and BFN, excessively high values may be responsible for low deposition of organic matter, leading to extinction of deposit feeders, and at the same time leading to elevated concentrations of suspended matter near the bottom, supporting suspension feeding community. Mechanisms and parameters of shear stress related to deposition and resuspension in ERSEM are based on values from Puls & Sündermann(1990). However, the default thresholds of bed shear velocity applied in ERSEM differ slightly from those published values. Additionally, Puls & Sündermann (1993) showed that critical shear velocities depend on environmental circumstances and published a range of values based on sediment type for erosion and particle sinking velocity for deposition. Here, we apply a correction to critical shear stress velocity based on the ranges given in Puls & Sündermann (1993). The correction factor follows a sigmoid function:

$$CF = \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\frac{gs-k}{r}}} \right) \cdot (C_{max} - C_{min}) + C_{min}$$

where CF is the resulting correction factor, C_{max} is the highest possible correction, C_{min} the lowest possible correction, k is the median grain size threshold where permeability starts, gs is the environmental median grain size and r is the rate of change (Figure 23). Here, we use the parameters $C_{max}= 0.51$, $C_{min}= 0.19$, $k = 221$ [μm], and $r = 70$. C_{max} and C_{min} are based on the

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differences between default ERSEM values and the parameters published in Puls & Sündermann (1993). $k = 221$ [μm], is based on the median grain size where permeability of the sediment is roughly 10^{-12} , which is the sediment permeability threshold where it starts acting like a sieve, capturing organic matter particles that originate from the water column (Huettel & Rusch, 2000). In applying the resulting correction, we assume that median sediment grain size affects deposition of particulates through permeability. The decrease in shear stress at large grain size allows us to correct deposition for potential retention of particles within permeable sediment.

Figure 23: Correction factor for shear stress, based on station-specific median sediment grain size (D50). Black sigmoid curve is the result of the correction factor calculation. Blue points are associated factors applied to stations based on their mean D50. Horizontal black lines denote C_{\max} (0.51) and C_{\min} (0.19), vertical red dashed line shows the centre point of the curve (221 microns). Station abbreviations are defined in the main text.

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It should be noted that the correction factor is applied to shear stress values ‘perceived’ in ERSEM, whereas the physical model remains unaffected. This approach allows us to implicitly account for filtering of organic matter through coarse non-cohesive sediments in a model that essentially represents cohesive, muddy environment. The impactful correction factor values (at least 0.51) originate from the fact that we change the underlying critical shear velocity parameter and that the effect on critical shear stress is a squared relationship.

Having applied the appropriate correction factors according to sediment grain size at our example locations FF and BFN we get the trajectories as shown on Figure 24.

Figure 24: Example runs of offline 0D benthic ERSEM with correction factor for shear stress forcing applied. Lines are ERSEM model predictions, points are MWTL observations. Blue colours are suspension feeders; black colours are deposit feeders. Thin lines are daily values; thick lines are yearly mean values. Example locations are Frisian Front and Broad Fourteens north (see Figure 21 map).

Here, modelled biomasses of both groups benefit from increased food supply, exceeding the observed values. Notably, biomass of deposit feeders at FF exceeds measured data ~4 times within 2 years (and ~2 times at BFN). Suspension feeders’ biomasses at FF are uniform and elevated compared to observational data, whereas BFN overestimation increases during the simulation period.

The applied correction to shear stress allows deposit feeders to proliferate where they were previously suppressed by low food supply. However, as in the example above, this correction can lead to unrealistically high concentrations. Therefore, we implemented two predatory functional groups into benthic ERSEM: infaunal predators and epifaunal predators. Although these groups were part of the original ERSEM development (Ebenhöh et al., 1995), subsequent configurations omitted them. Within NECCTON, in addition to the main function of applying top-down control on

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other macrozoobenthic groups, introducing predators has the goal of more realistic representation of shelf sea benthic food webs, and functional biodiversity in the model.

Infaunal predators mainly feed on deposit feeder biomass whereas epifaunal predators mainly feed on suspension feeder biomass. The MWTL data also includes carnivores, for which the simulations presented above neglect biomass. It must be noted that in comparisons with observational data, we treat infaunal and epifaunal predators as a single group. The combination of applying a shear stress correction and the inclusion of predators resulted in a better fit between model predictions and field values in most locations (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Example runs of offline 0D benthic ERSEM with correction factor for shear stress forcing and benthic predators. Lines are new ERSEM model predictions, points are MWTL observations. Blue colours are suspension feeders, black colours are deposit feeders and red colours are infaunal and epifaunal predators combined (in both model output and field data). Thin lines are daily values; thick lines are yearly mean values. Model runs on all 5 tested NS locations are shown (see Figure 21 map).

Notably, the model reproduced well the general pattern of observations, with relatively higher deposit feeder biomass, and lower biomass of suspension feeders and predators (where the former usually slightly exceeds the latter).

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For all model runs, model skill can be expressed as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which has the same units as the modelled values, or as Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), which is expressed in terms of relative change. Both these skill statistics are determined for each model run at each location. The values presented here are RMSE based on the total macrobenthic biomass (in mgC/m²) in observations and model predictions (Table 3). These results demonstrate that including epifaunal and infaunal predators into the benthic ERSEM ecosystem model, as well as applying a correction towards the shear stress, improves model predictions across all tested Dutch North Sea regions.

Table 3: Benthic ERSEM skill in predicting macrobenthic biomass, expressed as RMSE between the modelled and the observed values. The results are shown for combinations of model runs without (base) and with (predators) introducing new functional group, without (uncorrected) and with (corrected) implementation of correction factor for shear stress. Station abbreviations are given in the text.

Location	Base/uncorrected	Base/corrected	Predators/uncorrected	Predators/corrected
FF	2665	9120	2857	1119
DB	4000	6762	1257	1272
OG	2131	4842	2498	1377
BFN	2483	2926	2407	1213
BFS	1566	2860	1718	1553
Station average	2569	5302	2148	1307

Implementation of ERSEM in the FABM framework (Bruggeman & Bolding, 2014) allows easy coupling to a range of hydrodynamic models (physical hosts). Moreover, the model is often coupled to different versions of the same physical host or applied with different forcings and settings within the same model domain. While this approach allows for increased flexibility of applications, it leads to variability in the results of the biogeochemical model. For this reason, it is important to analyse the sensitivity of the benthic ERSEM module to pelagic inputs. The sensitivity of the new benthic ERSEM configuration was tested in the same setup as applied above by multiplying all phytoplankton or pelagic POM inputs to the model by a scalar ranging from 0.5 to 1.5. Sensitivity was tested at the BFN location for both the default ERSEM model and the updated version, which included predators (Figure 26a,b).

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Figure 26: Sensitivity of default benthic ERSEM (A) and the updated version with predators and shear stress correction (B) to pelagic inputs at location BFN. Feeding type: deposit feeders (depo) and suspension feeders (susp). Input type: phytoplankton (P) and particulate organic matter (R).

As expected, dietary preferences of suspension feeders resulted in greater sensitivity to changes in phytoplankton input, in contrast to more rapid response of deposit feeders to inputs of POM. As presented in Figure 26, the two model configurations yielded similar sensitivity of benthic biomass in terms of deposit feeders, but increased sensitivity of suspension feeder predictions towards phytoplankton input in the predator model. We attribute this difference largely to decreased absolute biomass predictions that align more closely with the field measurements in the predator model (compare blue lines in Figures 23 & 24).

4.1.4 Benthic macrofaunal predators: testing 3D implementation

To understand the impact of including benthic predators in ERSEM at a regional scale, we ran tests of the new implementations (described in section 4.1.3) in 3D, coupled with the hydrodynamic model NEMO, within the AMM7 domain (20°W -13°E and 40°N -65°N). The initial conditions used a 30-year spin up run of a standard NEMO-ERSEM configuration, repeating 1993-1997 six times. The total benthic macrofaunal biomass at each point was partitioned between the four macrofaunal groups in the same proportions as produced by Station L4 model setup of 1D (water column) GOTM-ERSEM output to enable inclusion of benthic predators in the initial condition. The model

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was run for the period 1993-2000. The values presented below represent means for the period 1998-2000.

Figure 27: Biomasses of modelled functional groups of macrobenthos on NWES from ERSEM configuration including benthic predators.

First, we performed a model test with benthic predators added, but without shear stress corrections (Figures 27-29). Benthic macrofaunal biomasses were highest on the shelf, with particularly high biomasses of all functional groups found in the shallow central North Sea. In accordance with their food matrix connection, spatial distribution of epibenthic predators closely resembled that of suspension feeders, whereas infaunal predators spatially resembled deposit feeders. The southern North Sea, English Channel, Irish and Celtic Seas had very low biomasses. Deposit feeder biomass was more uniformly distributed across the shelf than suspension feeder biomass, which was high in the central North Sea and select regions along the coastline. Similarly, epibenthic predator biomass was lower and spatially more constrained than infaunal predator biomass.

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Figure 28: Deposit feeder biomass from baseline ERSEM and the model version with benthic predators. The difference shows output with benthic predators included with the baseline subtracted.

Figure 29: Suspension feeder biomass from baseline ERSEM and the model version with benthic predators. The difference shows output with benthic predators included with the baseline subtracted.

The inclusion of macrozoobenthic predators in ERSEM on the distributions of macrofauna biomasses on the shelf generally leads to decreased biomass of both deposit and suspension feeders (Figures 28 and 29), particularly in the shallow regions of the North Sea and some coastal locations where biomass was previously highest.

Although including benthic predators improved predictions of benthic macrofauna in 1D (see section 4.1.3) and to some extent in 3D (by reducing unrealistically high biomasses in certain regions), the issue of low macrozoobenthic survival in hydrodynamically active areas (southern North Sea, English Channel, Irish Sea) remains, largely because of insufficient supply of particulate organic matter into the highly permeable sediments in these regions. We propose a solution and its implementation in 0D/1D settings but here we tested a crude approximation of this approach by uniformly reducing shear stresses passed to ERSEM to 30% of their value in the physical host model.

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Figure 30: Change to semi-labile particulate organic carbon in sediments in the experiment with uniformly reduced shear stress values.

Preliminary results (Figure 30) show increased semi-labile particulate organic carbon in the sediments, especially in locations with previously low organic carbon content. This increase in deposition/decrease in resuspension primarily affects hydrodynamically active areas, in effect implicitly accounting for material trapping within the matrix of permeable sediment, increasing its availability as a food source for benthic organisms. We have developed and performed initial tests of the NEMO-ERSEM AMM7 setup with the implementation of spatially varying scaling of the shear stress correction factor, accounting for sediment grain size. These ERSEM runs use maps of sediment grain size provided as external input, based on synthetic maps from Wilson et al. (2018). Further calibration and validation of the model will test for impacts of changes on benthic macrofauna and carbon fluxes across the benthic-pelagic interface.

4.2 The Black Sea

4.2.1 *Mytilus* DEB model calibration and growth performance in the Black Sea

We parameterized the individual DEB model for *M. galloprovincialis* physiology (Figure 3) for mussels in the Black Sea, noting that most DEB model parameters for *M. galloprovincialis* can be found in literature and are often applied successfully, since *Mytilus* is a typical model genus for DEB studies (Van Der Veer et al., 2006; Saraiva et al., 2012; Sarà et al., 2012; Monaco & McQuaid, 2018). However, we needed to calibrate the parameters for the filter feeding mechanism based on data, given that these parameters were only derived and validated for the sister species *M. edulis* in different biogeographical regions (North Sea / Baltic Sea) (Saraiva et al., 2012). Calibration of *Mytilus* feeding parameters was performed on growth data published by Karayucel et al. (2010) and Vural et al (2015). The former study published *Mytilus* growth on a raft culture near Sinop Bay, Turkey, whereas the latter published *Mytilus* growth data from bottom cultures in the Sea of

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Marmara. A third growth dataset, originating from Sevastopol Bay, and published by Chelyadina & Popov (2020), was then used to validate the predicted *Mytilus* shell growth trajectories. Figure 31 provides the published locations of the used growth time series.

Figure 31, Locations of individual growth datasets used to parametrize the *M. galloprovincialis* Black Sea DEB model.

To compare the developed DEB model with the growth data, we need adequate environmental timeseries of temperature, oxygen, phytoplankton, detritus and SIM. For all three locations, we obtained these environmental data from either 1) the published dataset itself, 2) published environmental data from a different peer reviewed literature source, but similar time and space, 3) reanalysis of Copernicus Marine Service data, in that order of priority.

Feeding parameters were calibrated using the Nelder-Mead and Levenberg-Marquart algorithms from the R *FME* package ((Soetaert & Petzoldt, 2010) and references therein). After calibrating model parameters based on shell length and wet weight data from the Sinop and Marmara locations, we plotted the DEB model alongside shell length data from all three locations to validate the effectiveness of individual DEB model growth performances (Figures 32-34). Sensitivity of model predictions towards the calibrated feeding parameters is visualized by letting the model runs iterate uniformly over parameter sets where all feeding parameters are simultaneously varied up to 15%.

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Figure 32. Field measurements from Karayucel et al. (2010) and DEB model predictions of *M. galloprovincialis* shell length and wet weight near Sinop Bay, showing model predictions (black line) and sensitivity envelope (shaded area). Sensitivity is calculated by varying all calibrated feeding parameters by up to 15%. Environmental temperature, chlorophyll a, detritus and SIM are given in the original publication, for O₂ modelled values were used.

Figure 33. Field measurements from Vural et al., (2015) and DEB model predictions of *M. galloprovincialis* shell length and wet weight near Sinop Bay, showing model predictions (black line) and sensitivity envelope (shaded area). Sensitivity is calculated by varying all calibrated feeding parameters by up to 15%. Environmental temperature, phytoplankton, detritus, and SIM are given in the original publication, O₂ was estimated based on Deniz & Taş (2009).

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Figure 34. Field measurements from Chelyadina et al. (2020) and DEB model predictions of *M. galloprovincialis* shell length in Sevastopol Bay, by measuring and modelling mussel dynamics for 2 different starting sizes, showing model predictions (black line) and sensitivity envelope (shaded area). Sensitivity is calculated by varying all calibrated feeding parameters by up to 15%. Environmental temperature is given in the original publication, noting that we modelled phytoplankton, detritus, and O₂ values, assuming SIM contains equal weights of detritus + phytoplankton.

We upscaled the individual DEB model to the Black Sea, using a 0d offline coupling, where we obtained time series data on temperature, oxygen, detritus, and phytoplankton from the NEMO-BAMHBI model for Black Sea biogeochemistry. We extracted data in a 2.5 by 2.5 km grid for the complete extent of the Black Sea for the temporal period 2000-2020. In each grid cell, the individual DEB model runs for 3 years. Given that DEB models a life history, the run does not converge to a stable average size, but instead to an asymptotic size. A three-year run was deemed the most accurate because a median age of 3 characterizes individuals within Black Sea mussel beds (Shurova & Gomoiu, 2006). Individual growth in each grid cell starts with minimal initial size, a recently settled juvenile.

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Figure 35: Mapped shell length that individuals reach after 3 years of undisturbed (no competition/mortality) growth. The Black Sea environmental data was obtained from CMEMS, and the map uses average years between 2000 and 2020 in each grid cell.

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4.2.2 *Mytilus* DEB-IBM biomass and density predictions in 0D offline coupling with the Black Sea biogeochemistry.

In order to model population density and biomass in addition to individual physiology, we included population dynamics in the DEB model, resulting in a DEB-IBM (Figure 6). The same individual physiological parameters govern DEB-IBM for *M. galloprovincialis* in the Black Sea, which also tracks several cohorts spawned from each spawning period. In the Black Sea, *M. galloprovincialis* spawning occurs twice per year, once in spring and once in autumn. During each spawning period, individuals release gametes as eggs, a fraction of which develop into pelagic larva, based on male/female ratio and initial egg mortality. These pelagic larvae then develop until they reach an individual biomass threshold above which they become competent pediveligers, the life stage at which they settle to the seafloor into a new cohort of mussels. The environmental factors shear stress and sediment type govern settlement rate of pelagic pediveliger larvae, capped at a maximum settlement rate of 500 ind/day for numerical stability. In the current 0d model configuration, forced by near-bottom NEMO-BAMHBI output, mussels consume phytoplankton, detritus, and oxygen from dynamic resource pools which are replenished by the forcing values via a dilution rate, similar to semi-chemostat dynamics. Temperature and phytoplankton concentration determine pelagic larval growth and mortality dynamics, but larvae do not consume resources in this model. Including the consumption of resources by mussels in the population dynamics model is crucial in order to avoid all mussel bed biomasses growing indefinitely. Parameters for population dynamics, such as mortality rate and larval growth rate are all estimated based on a combination of published literature and cohort-wise population decline observed by Karayucel et al. (2010) and Vural et al (2015).

Similar to the individual DEB physiology model, we ran the DEB-IBM for mussel biomass and density in a 0D offline fashion and looped over each grid cell of the NEMO-BAHMBI domain (Grégoire et al., 2025). This parametrization is preliminary and therefore the results may not be final. The resulting map of predicted biomasses (Figure 36) shows very high biomasses near the coast of the Northwestern Shelf, low but stable population biomasses in the middle of the continental shelf, and no biomass in the deep anoxic central zone of the Black Sea, as expected. We compared model output, in terms of wet weight biomass [WW/m²] and population density [ind/m²] to benthic field measurements of *M. galloprovincialis* beds from several published field campaigns, and show data points from Teaca et al. (2016) (biomass points on map Figure 36 and Figure 37, n = 88). Model skill, expressed as mean absolute scaled error (MASE), for density predictions was 1.63, and for biomass was 0.93. A MASE value below 1 indicates that the model predicts the observed value better than the mean observed value. Therefore, although the model can predict biomass, the current parametrization predicts density values poorly.

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Figure 36: Mussel bed biomass [mmolC/m²] predictions of *M. galloprovincialis* DEB-IBM in the Black Sea. Red points on the map are field measurement locations showing the biomass of *M. galloprovincialis* sampled. The DEB-IBM was forced with the average year of forcings between 2000 and 2020 of temperature, phytoplankton, detritus, oxygen, SIM, and shear stress.

Figure 37: Direct comparison between model predictions (MOD) of the 0d (offline) DEB-IBM and field measurements (FIELD) of density ([ind/m²], left) and biomass ([WW/m²], right). Each point in the graph combines a field measurement and the predicted model value at a given set of coordinates. Colours show the sediment type of the grid cell at the measurement point.

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4.2.3 *Phyllophora* red seaweed growth and biomass in the Black Sea based physiological model

To parametrize the macroalgal model for *Phyllophora* biomass in the Black Sea (Figure 8), we obtained *Phyllophora crispa* or *Phyllophora truncata* (*Coccolytus truncatus*) specific nutrient uptake (Wallentinus, 1984), temperature-dependent photosynthesis (Mathieson & Norall, 1975) and respiration (Johansson & Snoeijs, 2002) rates from the literature. Additional unknown parameters in the currently developed macroalgae model were calibrated on *Phyllophora* rope growth culture in the Jarylgachsky Gulf (Blinova & Trishina, 1990). Lack of quality biomass and growth data in the Black Sea precluded a separate validation of *Phyllophora* biomass. The same growth trajectory also demonstrates model sensitivity (Figure 38). The figures showing model behaviour also use the current parametrization (Figures 9 and 10).

Figure 38: *Phyllophora* biomass growth trajectory used for parametrization. Points are biomass rope culture measurements from Blinova & Trishina (1990) from 1984-1985 in Jarylgachsky Gulf, Crimea (showing only 1 of 4 published growth trajectories). Data are originally provided in relative growth units, assuming starting biomass (13 gWW) for data and model run. The calibrated model (black line) output [WW/m²] is generated by using environmental forcings of Jarylgachsky Gulf described by Blinova & Trishina (1990) (temperature & oxygen) and CMEMS (nutrients & light). Calculation of the model sensitivity envelope allows the five most sensitive parameters to vary uniformly by 10% (shaded areas).

Environmental data from the Black Sea, between 2000 and 2020, was downloaded from CMEMS and averaged to show *Phyllophora* biomass growth patterns over a broad biogeographical range. This model assessment set the runtime to 10 years, to ensure proximity of the shown biomass to

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the stable state, which is usually reached within 2000 days (Figure 10). Grid cell specific environmental habitat conditions resulted in stable estimates for each grid cell individually. In order to show the effect of turbidity, and potentially eutrophication, of Black Sea waters on *Phyllophora* growth, we created 4 maps with different levels of turbidity (light extinction per meter depth) (Figure 39). Construction of the biomass maps also assumes that *Cystoseira* communities dominate shallow regions (Afanasyev et al., 2017), and that their biomass competes for light with *Phyllophora*, similar to Figure 11. Note that competition between the two macroalgal species occurs only for light and not for nutrients.

Figure 39: *Phyllophora* biomass maps resulting from the Black Sea macroalgae model. Light is limited by depth and the light extinction term, turbidity [m] (varied in the 4 maps). Additionally, light at the bottom depends on competition from *Cystoseira* community biomass. Additional environmental time series are modelled data.

To analyse the effect of eutrophication on the proliferation of on benthic macroalgae, the model allows us to include the colour-specific light attenuation effect of phytoplankton shading separately, by providing the depth average chlorophyll-a concentration of the overlying water column. By allowing phytoplankton shading, we needed to reduce the general, spatially constant turbidity (hereafter assumed to only incorporate SPM) to significantly lower levels to predict proliferation of *Phyllophora* biomass (Figure 40).

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Figure 40: *Phyllophora* biomass maps resulting from the Black Sea macroalgae model. Bottom light is limited by depth, phytoplankton shading (based on CMEMS data), competition from *Cystoseira* community biomass, and a spatially homogenous light extinction term, turbidity [1/m]. Additional environmental time series are modelled data.

From the resulting maps, we conclude that the North Western Shelf of the Black Sea and the southwestern region represent the only locations that contain habitat suitable for *Phyllophora* growth. Additionally, because of its deep living nature, turbidity has an extreme light limiting effect on *Phyllophora* and thus high turbidity drastically decreased potential community biomass (compare Figures 39 and 40). Differences between these maps show the effect of spatial heterogeneity of chlorophyll-a. These results point to eutrophication in the Black Sea as one of the main reasons for the decline in *Phyllophora* biomass. A similar pattern emerged in the model assessment of Figure 11, where the inclusion of chlorophyll a in the water column decreased the potential growing habitat of *Phyllophora* in terms of parameter space.

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5. Conclusions

The model developments undertaken within NECCTON Task 6.2.4 represent advances in benthic ecosystem modelling capabilities across two distinct marine regions. The enhanced ERSEM configuration for the North West European Shelf addresses long-standing issues of inadequate representation of benthic macrofaunal biomass by including predator functional groups and refined treatment of sediment-water interactions. The combination of infaunal and epifaunal predators with modified shear stress parameterisation substantially improved model skill in reproducing spatial distributions of observed macrofaunal biomass patterns across different functional types.

For the Black Sea, the development of species-specific models for mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Phyllophora* provide new tools for understanding benthic ecosystem dynamics in this unique environment. The DEB-IBM approach for mussels successfully captures individual growth and population-level processes under varying environmental conditions, whereas the physiological model for *Phyllophora* incorporates critical light dynamics necessary for deep-water macroalgae modelling. Both models demonstrate reasonable skill in reproducing observed patterns.

Although the described model developments significantly improved model performance, low spatial coverage and high variability in observational data, and challenges in unit conversions still constrained validation capabilities. The analysis of long-term time series at Station L4 demonstrated the difficulty of extracting clear seasonal signals from highly variable benthic communities, emphasising the need for continued monitoring to achieve improved understanding of benthic ecosystem dynamics that would, in turn, inform further development of process-based benthic models.

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